

T1 ρ -based dynamic glucose-enhanced (DGE ρ) MRI at 3 T – method development and early clinical experience in the human brain

Kai Herz^{1,2}, Tobias Lindig^{1,3*}, Anagha Deshmane¹, Jens Schittenhelm⁴, Marco Skardelly⁵, Benjamin Bender³, Ulrike Ernemann³, Klaus Scheffler^{1,6}, Moritz Zaiss¹

¹ Magnetic Resonance Center, Max Planck Institute for Biological Cybernetics, Tübingen, Germany

² IMPRS for Cognitive and Systems Neuroscience, University of Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany

³ Department of Diagnostic and Interventional Neuroradiology, University Hospital Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany

⁴ Department of Neuropathology, University Hospital Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany

⁵ Department of Neurosurgery, University Hospital Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany

⁶ Department of Biomedical Magnetic Resonance, University Hospital Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany

***Corresponding author:**

Tobias Lindig

Department of Diagnostic and Interventional Neuroradiology

University Hospital Tübingen

Hoppe-Seyler-Str. 3

72076 Tübingen

phone +49 7071 2986024

email tobias.lindig@med.uni-tuebingen.de

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Abstract

Purpose: The aim of this study was to translate the T1 ρ -based dynamic glucose-enhanced (DGE ρ) experiment from ultra-high magnetic field strengths to a clinical field strength of 3 T. While the protocol would seem to be as simple as Gadolinium enhanced imaging, several obstacles had to be addressed, including SNR, robustness of contrast, and post-processing, especially motion correction.

Methods: Spin-lock based pre-saturation and a 3D gradient-echo snapshot readout were optimized for 3 T with regard to robustness, CEST effect strength and SNR. Post processing steps, including dynamic B₀ and motion correction, were analyzed and optimized in seven healthy volunteers. The final protocol including glucose injection was applied to three glioblastoma patients.

Results: With appropriate post-processing, motion-related artifacts could be drastically reduced, and an SNR of approximately 90 could be achieved for a single dynamic measurement. In two patients with blood-brain barrier breakdown a significant glucose uptake could be observed with a DGE ρ effect strength in the range of 0.4 % of the water signal. Thorough analysis of possible residual motion revealed that the statistical evidence can decrease when tested against pseudo effects due to uncorrected motion.

Conclusion: DGE ρ imaging was optimized for clinical field strengths of 3 T and a robust protocol was established for broader application. Early experience shows that DGE ρ seems possible at 3 T, and could not only be attributed to motion artifacts. Observed DGE ρ maps showed unique patterns, partly matching with the T1-ce tumor ring enhancement. However, effect sizes are small and careful clinical application is necessary.

Keywords: dynamic glucose enhancement, DGE ρ , glucoCEST, CEST, CESL, chemical exchange saturation transfer

Introduction

Chemical exchange saturation transfer (CEST) MRI allows imaging of metabolites by employing the chemical exchange of metabolite protons and the water pool protons. CEST effects can be detected in vivo which has been shown for e.g. amide protons of proteins and peptides^{1,2}, guanidinium protons of creatine³, amine protons of glutamate⁴, as well as hydroxyl groups of glycosamine⁵, glycogen⁶ and sugars⁷⁻¹¹. The hydroxyl CEST effect of glucose gives the opportunity for approved injection experiments in humans to study the differences in the CEST signals upon glucose injection, enabling the use of natural D-glucose as an MRI contrast agent. Such experiments observing CEST signal changes before and after injection, have been shown feasible in animal experiments^{7,8,12,13} and humans at ultra-high fields¹⁴⁻¹⁷. In a dynamic glucose enhanced (DGE) imaging protocol, labeled images are acquired before, during and after the glucose injection in a repetitive scheme to observe dynamic changes due to the glucose injection^{13,14}. The observed DGE signal is assumed to originate from the vascular compartment, as well as from glucose molecules that leak through the blood-brain barrier (BBB) to the extravascular and extracellular space^{7,14}. In the healthy brain, glucose uptake signals are expected to originate from extra- and intracellular compartments⁸, while in tumorous regions, where the metabolism to lactate is typically very fast, the intracellular contribution to the DGE signal is expected to be small⁷. However, previous in-vivo studies at 9.4 T found a correlation between [¹⁸F]FDG-autoradiography and glucoCEST¹², suggesting that cellular uptake and metabolism products of glucose might also contribute to the signal. Thus, glucose has potential as a functional MR contrast agent.

While DGE could be shown to be feasible in humans at ultra-high field (UHF), little has been published at 3 T^{18,19}, and robust translation to clinical field strengths remains an open challenge. This is mainly due to lower SNR and smaller CEST effect size at 3 T due to the strong direct water saturation. At the same time the difference method DGE is prone to motion artifacts²⁰ which makes generation of stable contrast very difficult. However, implementation on a clinical scanner would be desirable, as the injection experiment

could be included in a regular clinical protocol, making it convenient for physicians and patients.

To overcome the obstacles at 3 T we combined several recent developments: (i) the DGE effect strength was recently optimized based on quantitative CEST experiments²¹. These optimal parameters were used and implemented with (ii) a novel adiabatic pulse shape designed for off-resonant spin-lock (SL) experiments²² which is favorable as it has lower direct water saturation and high CEST labeling efficiency. (iii) A 3D gradient-echo snapshot readout²³ was used for imaging of the CEST prepared signal to limit motion artifacts, and to be able to perform volume registration of the acquired dynamic scans retrospectively. An additional dynamic B_0 correction was realized using the phase information of the gradient echo acquisition. To emphasize the $T_{1\rho}$ -based approach using SL pulses, the dynamic glucose enhanced imaging is referred to as DGE ρ hereafter.

After optimization of the CEST pre-saturation pulses, the snapshot readout for 3 T and the post processing (correction of motion and dynamic field changes) in seven healthy volunteers, the DGE ρ method was applied to three high grade brain tumor patients, two of them with visible BBB breakdown.

Methods

Saturation pulse optimization

As shown previously, SL pulses have a higher exchange weighting than classical saturation pulses such as Gaussian or rectangular shaped pulses especially in the intermediate to fast exchange regime²⁴. Recently published adiabatic prepared SL pulses²² allow for stable saturation at off-resonant frequencies with low direct water saturation. Because they were previously optimized for $B_0 = 9.4$ T, this optimization was repeated for $B_0 = 3$ T. The adiabatic pulses are defined by the adiabatic parameter μ , the bandwidth Δf , and the Hamming window size t_{window} and duration t_{adia} . The optimization method was the same as in Herz et al.²², with Z-spectra simulated between -3 to 3 ppm using 500 spectral samples. To guarantee a stable adiabatic tipping, t_{adia} was set to 12 ms and the pulse was simulated for different B_1 (85, 95, 100, 110%) and ΔB_0 (-0.15, -0.1,

-0.05, 0, 0.05 ppm) values, typical for the 3 T system, resulting in 20 Z-spectra per parameter combination. Parameters were varied between $5 \leq \mu \leq 100$, $1 \text{ kHz} \leq \Delta f \leq 10 \text{ kHz}$, and $0.5 \text{ ms} \leq t_{\text{window}} \leq 12 \text{ ms}$. To achieve a maximum effect size, the amplitude was set to $4 \mu\text{T}$ and the locking time TSL was set to 120 ms, based on previous numerical optimization²¹.

Readout optimization

To detect small CEST effects in the order of 1 %, a sequence with sufficient SNR is indispensable. At the same time, a fast readout avoids motion artifacts during the readout and allows for volume co-registration of the dynamic scans. To compromise these needs a fast RF-spoiled 3D gradient-echo based snapshot-CEST sequence was used²³. As this was also initially optimized for 9.4 T, parameters were adapted for 3 T²⁵. The base resolution and the bandwidth per pixel were varied to find a sufficient SNR in an acceptable readout duration. Images were acquired with either $1.7 \times 1.7 \text{ mm}^2$ or $2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^2$ in plane resolution with 80 % FOV in the first phase-encoding direction and 400 or 700 Hz/px bandwidth. TE/TR was set to 2.5/5 ms for 400 Hz/px and 2/4 ms for 700 Hz/px bandwidth. Twelve slices with 5 mm slice thickness were acquired at a flip angle of 6° . Parallel imaging acceleration factor 2 was applied in the phase encoding direction with GRAPPA reconstruction performed offline. SNR was calculated using the pseudo multiple replica method²⁶ with 100 replicas, and averaged over the different frequency offsets that were acquired in the DGE ρ measurement.

Post-processing optimization

To optimize motion correction, different algorithms were tested with optimized parameters, namely AFNI²⁷, elastix²⁸ and SPM²⁹. As a test, all images of one frequency offset were registered to the first image acquired at that offset. The parameters used for the motion correction algorithms can be found in the Supporting Information. Results were then analyzed using the normalized mutual information, calculated from a joint histogram with 256 bins. In addition, a visual analysis was performed to identify obvious residual motion artifacts.

As shown by Windschuh et al.³⁰, the change of the B_0 inhomogeneity field during the measurement can have an effect on the analysis of CEST effects, and can be corrected dynamically using gradient echo phase maps. To test the influence of these field changes on DGE ρ data at 3 T, the correction was adapted, implemented and used for the dynamic data in this work.

MRI Measurements

The final DGE ρ imaging protocol consists of repeated blocks containing three elements: (i) a relaxation period of 4 s, (ii) the saturation phase with one adiabatic SL pulse of 4 μ T and 120 ms locking time, followed by (iii) the snapshot GRE readout. The dynamic measurement included an unsaturated M_0 scan at the beginning, followed by 160 measurements saturated at five different frequency offsets (-300, 0.6, 0.9, 1.2 and 1.5 ppm) forming a group of scans which were subsequently repeated, resulting in 32 measurements of each frequency offset. Measurements at these different frequency offsets allow for a retrospective dynamic B_0 correction. The final protocol had a temporal resolution of approx. 6.3 s per scan, 31 s per group of scans, and 16:45 min scan time in total. All imaging was performed at 3 T (Prisma, Siemens Healthcare, Erlangen, Germany) using the vendor's 64-channel head coil for signal reception, and the single channel body coil for RF transmission.

Healthy subject and patient measurements were performed after acquiring written informed consent from all participants prior to examination. The prospective cross-sectional study was approved by the local ethics review board. In total 10 subjects were scanned, 7 healthy subjects and 3 patients with a high-grade brain tumor. Three healthy volunteers were scanned in a first step to optimize the readout for SNR and the motion correction algorithm. The final protocol was then applied in four healthy volunteers without glucose injection to demonstrate the baseline robustness. The three patients, all diagnosed with glioblastomas, were scanned before biopsy: Patient 1 (70y, m) was diagnosed with a histopathologically proven glioblastoma WHO \circ IV, molecular profile: IDH1-wildtype, MGMT-promoter unmethylated, ATRX retained. Patient 2 (61y, f) was diagnosed with a histopathologically proven glioblastoma WHO \circ IV, molecular profile: IDH1-wildtype, MGMT-promoter unmethylated, ATRX retained. Patient 3 (54y, f) was

diagnosed with a histopathologically proven glioblastoma WHO °IV, molecular profile: IDH1-wildtype, MGMT-promoter methylated to marginal value, ATRX retained. The patient measurements included an intra-venous D-glucose injection (0.3 g D-glucose/kg body weight, Glucosteril® 20%, Fresenius Kabi Deutschland GmbH, Bad Homburg, Germany) during the DGE ρ measurement, to detect dynamic changes. Blood glucose levels were measured using a conventional blood glucose meter (ACCU-CHEK® Aviva III, Roche Diabetes Care GmbH, Mannheim, Germany).

DGE ρ Contrast

Before data analysis, all images were volume registered in a two-step procedure. First, the first image of each offset group was registered to the very first M_0 image. In the second step, all following images of this offset group were registered to the transformed first image of the corresponding group. Z images were then generated using the corresponding image at -300 ppm as normalization: $Z_i(\Delta\omega) = S_i(\Delta\omega)/S_i(-300 \text{ ppm})$ with $1 \leq i \leq 32$. For 0.6, 0.9, 1.2 and 1.5 ppm, ΔDGE_{ρ} was calculated using the mean of the first six images per offset as a baseline Z_{ref} : $\Delta DGE_{\rho i}(\Delta\omega) = Z_{ref}(\Delta\omega) - Z_i(\Delta\omega)$. The very first unsaturated scan was applied to ensure steady-state magnetization at the end of the readout for the first S_0 image ($S_1(-300 \text{ ppm})$). The DGE ρ signal was filtered in time dimension by a box filter to get a more stable signal: $\Delta DGE_{\rho i} = (\Delta DGE_{\rho i-1} + \Delta DGE_{\rho i} + \Delta DGE_{\rho i+1})/3$. For visualization, ΔDGE_{ρ} maps were also spatially smoothed using a Gaussian filter with a convolution kernel size of 6 mm.

Glucose injection protocol

Blood samples were taken before and after the MR measurement to measure the blood glucose level. Patients were positioned and an anatomical reference scan was measured for slice positioning. Then the 17 minute long DGE ρ scan was started. The first 3 minutes were used for baseline scanning, after which glucose was injected, taking between 2 and 2.5 minutes. Thus, approximately 12 minutes of measurement time was left after complete glucose injection.

Results

Adiabatic spin lock pulses for 3 T saturation pulses

The aim was to achieve off-resonant adiabatic SL pulses without oscillation artifacts by optimizing μ , Δf , and t_{window} . The optimal parameter combination for the HSExp pulse was $\mu = 65$, $t_{\text{window}} = 3.5$ ms and $\Delta f = 2500$ Hz, resulting in a sum of squared deviations (SSD) of 0.0282. The SSD value as a function of the adiabatic parameters is shown in Figure 1a-c. Figure 1e shows measured gray matter (GM) and white matter (WM) Z-spectra after SL preparation with the proposed pulses revealing a smooth signal and no visible SL oscillation artifacts. Thus, arbitrary off-resonant SL experiments are possible at 3 T.

Readout

Figure 2 shows the average SNR over the five frequency offsets for different base resolutions and bandwidths. The used parameters and the resulting mean SNR values in different tissues are shown in Table 1. Although setting (B) showed the highest SNR, we chose the parameter combination (C). This was due to the 20% shorter TR which results in a higher temporal resolution, allowing for more averaging, which will also increase the effective SNR. Furthermore, shorter TR is expected to generate a higher contrast-to-noise ratio²³ and is less prone to motion during acquisition.

Post-processing

Motion Correction

The elastix motion correction algorithm resulted in a higher normalized mutual information compared to the AFNI and SPM algorithms. To visualize residual motion artifacts, all images were denoised after motion correction, and the registered source images were then subtracted from the reference image. The elastix algorithm showed the fewest residual artifacts (Figure 3).

Interleaved M_0 scan and dynamic B_0 correction

As the full DGE ρ scan time is rather long, potential artifacts get larger in magnitude with time. In addition to volume mismatch, further motion related artifact sources include varying coil sensitivities, altered slab selection, and B_0 field alterations. To prevent artifacts due to these effects, two correction methods were applied on the data. First, the

normalization with dynamic M_0 scans was used to prevent signal changes due to coil sensitivities and slab selection, as both affect the normalization scan in the same manner. Second, dynamic B_0 correction was applied to reduce artifacts resulting from B_0 field alterations leading to saturation pulses at different effective frequency offsets. The results of these two correction steps after motion correction for a healthy volunteer are shown in Figure 4. Figure 4a shows the $DGE\rho$ signal at 0.9 ppm at the center slice, 8 minutes after the start of the measurement, when using only the first M_0 scan to normalize the saturated images. The left hemisphere appears hypo-intense. The effect of an interleaved M_0 normalization can be seen in Figure 4b, where the left hemisphere no longer appears hypo-intense. However, the anterior region still shows a negative $DGE\rho$ contrast which visually correlates with the ΔB_0 map (Figure 4d). After a dynamic B_0 correction, this region appears brighter, resulting in a more flat image (Figure 4c). Figure 4e shows the histograms for the slices in 4a (yellow), 4b (red) and 4c (blue). Fitting the histogram with a normal distribution results in distributions of mean values and standard deviations of -0.25 ± 0.251 for Figure 4a, -0.137 ± 0.24 for Figure 4b, and -0.032 ± 0.208 for Figure 4c, supporting the hypothesis that an interleaved M_0 scan and a dynamic B_0 correction mitigates artifacts in this experiment. With this post-processing step, the final method is established.

Patient measurements

Figure 5 shows the clinical images for patient 1 (70y; glioblastoma WHO °IV; IDH1-wildtype; MGMT-promoter unmethylated; ATRX retained) together with the $DGE\rho$ contrast acquired at 3 T. For a dynamic analysis, three ROIs were drawn in the following regions: ROI 1 defined by the Gadolinium (Gd) uptake in a clinical T_1 -ce image, ROI 2 in the necrosis region inside of the Gd ring enhancement and ROI 3 in normal appearing white matter, ventral to Gd ring enhancement. All ROIs were defined in the T_1 -ce image (Figure 5a) which was registered to the saturated CEST image (Figure 5c). In both ROI 1 and 2, $\Delta DGE\rho$ was observed to increase after the glucose injection. The maximum $\Delta DGE\rho$ and the standard error in the Gd enhancing region (ROI 1) approximately 8 minutes after injection start was 0.38 ± 0.03 %; this was a significant signal increase compared to the baseline scans ($P < 0.005$; see Figure 8a). The WM (ROI 3) showed a

maximum signal of 0.1 ± 0.07 % during the glucose injection phase. The necrosis (ROI 2) showed a maximum signal of 0.35 ± 0.02 % approximately 2 minutes after glucose injection (Figure 5b), followed by a slow decrease of the signal. Measured blood glucose levels before and after the MR measurement were 111 mg/dl and 158 mg/dl respectively. After image number 25, the patient had a severe head movement (Figure 5d) which could not be retrospectively corrected. Directly after that movement, the entire $DGE\rho$ contrast is heavily affected. Here, also the WM showed a clear change that was not observed in precedent scans.

Clinical images as well as the $\Delta DGE\rho$ signal of patient 2 (61y; glioblastoma WHO °IV; IDH1-wildtype; MGMT-promoter unmethylated; ATRX retained) are shown in Figure 6. As this patient did not show any Gd enhancement and had no visible necrosis, only two ROIs were drawn for analysis: ROI 1 in normal appearing WM, and ROI 2 in a hypointense region. ROIs were again drawn in the T_1 -ce (Figure 6a) image that was co-registered to the first saturated CEST image (6c). Here, ROI 2 did not show significant $DGE\rho$ contrast except for some negative outlier measurements (see Figure 8a). Measured blood glucose levels before and after MRI were 93 mg/dl and 134 mg/dl, respectively. A small movement was observed in image number 30, which did not have a strong effect on the motion corrected $\Delta DGE\rho$ signal. While no significance could be observed, small regions of positive $\Delta DGE\rho$ signal appeared. As this patient suffers from gliomatosis, large areas of the brain are expected to be a heterogeneous tumor, where typical radiological features of high-grade gliomas with hypervascularisation and necrosis are missing³¹. Therefore, it might be possible that the appearing spots are actually true positive $DGE\rho$ effects. Here an improved sequence with higher SNR would be necessary for a solid statement.

Figure 7 shows the same analysis for patient 3 (54y; glioblastoma WHO °IV; IDH1-wildtype; MGMT-promoter methylated to marginal value; ATRX retained). Similar to the $\Delta DGE\rho$ signal of patient 1, the ROI corresponding with a Gd uptake (Figure 7a), showed a significant increase in $\Delta DGE\rho$ after the start of the glucose injection (see Figure 8a). An ROI drawn in a contralateral, normal appearing WM region showed only a minor $DGE\rho$ signal increase. The signal change in the tumor ROI was smaller than for patient 1 (~0.3%). In addition, the $DGE\rho$ images show several regions with increased signal

outside of the Gd enhanced region. Measured blood glucose levels before and after the MR measurement were 154 mg/dl and 201 mg/dl, respectively. For this patient, less movement compared to patient 1 was observed. However, there was a continuous, gradual shift (Figure 7d).

To investigate the significance of the DGE_{ρ} signal at each time point, ROIs of all 3 patients were analyzed statistically for the full dynamic experiment by applying two different tests. First, a one-sampled t-test was performed, with the null hypothesis that the voxels in the Gd-enhanced ROI (hypo-intense ROI for patient 2) appear in a zero-mean distribution. This test was performed for every measurement at the 0.6 ppm offset. The p-values for all three patients over time are shown in Figure 8a. The dashed line indicates the p-value threshold for rejecting the null hypothesis at a significance level of 0.005. The analysis supports the previous observations, especially for patient 2 and 3. For patient 2, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected at a single time point, apart from three outlier measurements. The same is observed for patient 3, until the glucose injection time period, after which the ΔDGE_{ρ} signal in the ROI differs significantly, with decreasing p-values for later measurements. The p-values for patient 1 are extremely scattered and the plotted values had to be clipped. The null hypothesis could only be confirmed for two time points before injection and interestingly also for five measurement points after the severe motion occurred.

To exclude influences of global contrast changes in the analysis, a two-sampled t-test was performed with the null hypothesis that the DGE_{ρ} values in the Gd-enhanced ROI (hypo-intense ROI for Patient 2) are equal with the mean values in the normal appearing WM ROI. The p-values for all three patients over time are shown in Figure 8b. Here, we could observe similar results as in the first test: the null hypothesis for patient 2 could not be rejected at a single time point. The same was true for patient 3, until the end of the glucose injection, after which the ΔDGE_{ρ} signal in the ROIs differ significantly, with decreasing p-values for later measurements. Even though the p-values show some outliers at image number 26-28 and 32, the general trend is clearly visible. For patient 1, a similar trend of decreasing p-values can be surmised, while the values are again much more scattered. For both curves we find that the DGE_{ρ} signal and contrast in tumor tissue

becomes significant around the expected maximum of the dynamic glucose signal of about 8-10 minutes³².

Figure 9 shows the T₂-FLAIR (a,e,i), T₁-ce (b,f,j), T₁-ce with overlaid Δ DGE ρ map (c,g,k) and the Δ DGE ρ -maps (d,h,l) of patients 1 (a-d), 2 (e-h) and 3 (i-l) for the time points indicated with a star in Figures 5b, 6b and 7b. All images were co-registered to the T₂-FLAIR image using SPM. The overlap of the Δ DGE ρ -map with the Gd ring enhancement for patients 1 and 3 can be appreciated in Figures 9c and 9k, respectively. Δ DGE ρ -maps for all slices can be found in the Supporting Information (Supporting Figure S16).

Additional extensive tests regarding motion and motion correction for patient 1 and 3 can be found in the Supporting Information as well. This analysis revealed that the DGE ρ signal in patient 1 is not significantly correlated with residual motion, while results for patient 3 showed a very weak voxel-wise correlation, with a coefficient of determination $R^2 = 2.52\%$.

Discussion

In this work, we aimed to translate DGE ρ MRI to the clinical field strength of 3 T. We presented the important steps – discussed in more detail below – to achieve an MRI method with glucose weighting, sufficiently high SNR, and robustness against concomitant influences of a dynamic scan. By using an optimized protocol for 3D readout, saturation and post-processing, the observed DGE ρ effect was only 0.4% of the water MRI signal at 3 T. The second finding, which is more implicit but even more important at this stage, is that a naive protocol without putting effort into mitigating the mentioned issues might lead to false positive as well as false negative findings. Effect sizes in a tumorous area can drop e.g. from 2 % for uncorrected data (see Supporting Figure S1) down to 0.4 % for motion corrected data. In the following, we want to discuss our observed DGE ρ signals and signal patterns in the context of previous findings at UHF in both animals and humans, as well as the influence of motion on the interpretation of DGE ρ signals. Finally, our methodological advancements are put into context.

The optimal method studied herein is off-resonant SL, yet off-resonant SL and CEST are very similar as shown previously^{22,24,33,34}. We think that SL has several advantages over a CEST experiment, especially in experiments close to the water resonance using high B_1 power where CEST is tricky and prone to instabilities even with shaped pulses. However, our insights should translate to all kinds of off-resonant CEST experiments, including low power approaches where CEST and off-resonant SL become even more similar. The prerequisite is that off-resonant oscillations are under control, which is possible using simple shaped pulses as shown by Zaiss et al²¹. Of course, one must be aware of certain differences between glucose-weighted CEST and off-resonant SL methods. Most importantly, they should be compared at the same power level and saturation time.

DGE ρ effect size in brain tumors at 3 T

The observed signal of 0.4 % is rather small compared to reported effects at 7 T in humans of 2-6 %^{14,17}. Using Bloch simulations, the signal drop due to translation from 7 T to 3 T was calculated to be a factor of 0.3 – 0.5²¹. Thus, the measured effect is smaller than expected but still in the correct order of magnitude. The maximum effect size was observed approximately 8 and 9 minutes after beginning the glucose injection for patient 1 and patient 3, respectively, which is in good agreement with Jin et al.³² who reported a peak of the DGE ρ signal in the tumor after 8 – 10 minutes. Interestingly, this time course can also be observed in the significance plot in Figure 8a.

DGE ρ contrast pattern in brain tumors

Vascular¹⁴ as well as intracellular contributions⁸ to the DGE signal are still discussed in the literature. However, the community agrees that a large fraction of the glucoCEST signal originates from glucose that leaks through a damaged BBB into the extravascular, extracellular space⁷. As Gadolinium based contrast agents would also enter this extracellular space in regions with a BBB breakdown, one would expect a correlation between dynamic contrast enhanced (DCE) images using Gd and DGE images. Animal studies reported various findings: Walker Samuel et al. did not find a significant correlation between Gd-enhancement and glucoCEST¹², while Jin et al. reported a correlation of DCE with an early glucoCEST response³². Previous studies in humans at 7T observed different patterns of DGE and DCE^{14,16,17} as well.

In our data, we made the following observations: first, with a visible BBB breakdown observed in patient 1 and 3 a positive DGE ρ signal could also be detected. However, only a coarse match with the tumor region outlined by the Gadolinium enhanced region was observed, and the hyperintensity patterns in DGE ρ did not fully match the DCE patterns. This was also supported by voxel wise statistical analysis between DGE ρ and DCE in a larger tumor ROI (see Supporting Figures S14 and S15, $P > 0.005$). In summary, the observed DGE ρ maps show unique patterns, partly matching with the tumor ring enhancement. Whether the observed hot spots in the DGE ρ maps originate from higher glucose levels or lower pH values with higher tumor activity is beyond our judgement and requires additional patient data. We believe that final conclusions about the relation between DGE and DCE in the human brain requires more data, and as well higher contrast to noise ratio of DGE. It could be that some of the differences we observe are still due to the lower sensitivity of DGE compared to DCE.

The contribution of intravascular glucose to the entire glucoCEST signal is expected to be low due to the higher pH in the vascular space, as discussed in previous studies^{7,8,10}. However, in larger arteries Xu et al.¹⁴ and Knutsson et al.³⁵ showed strong CEST signal uptake with correlation to the blood glucose level, which we could detect using SL in neither this nor in previous studies^{15,17}. This discrepancy can be investigated in further studies, but for now we have no explanation for that.

Potential additional origins of contrast

Besides glucose hydroxyl CEST signals, other effects might contribute to the observed signal upon glucose injection, such as changes of osmolality, flow and oxygenation level of blood, and even volume changes of blood and CSF. Regarding osmolality, both osmotic effects and glucose concentration would lower the Z-value after injection. Nasrallah et al.¹⁰ showed that glucoCEST is insensitive to osmolality effects, and Jin et al.³⁶ reported a small effect with glucoCESL which would even decrease in the tumor because glucose molecules can enter the extravascular-extracellular space via blood-brain barrier leakage³². Thus, we would not expect a large contribution due to osmolality changes. The same applies for cerebral blood flow, as Walker-Samuel et al.¹² did not see any changes in blood flow or pH in a previous animal study and could exclude

concomitant effects due to hyperglycemia as a source of contrast for glucoCEST. According to Purnell et al.³⁷ glucose injections can alter blood oxygenation levels detectable by a BOLD effect change of approximately 1 %, however, in our dynamically normalized DGE ρ signals the T_2^* /BOLD-weighting cancels out, as nicely shown by Khlebnikov et al.³⁸. A CSF volume change on the contrary could introduce a contrast change due to non-linear deformations in the images, which is discussed in more detail in the next paragraph. Finally, metabolite products of glucose might also contribute to the uptake, such as phosphorylated glucose and amino acids¹² as well as lactate³⁹, although the amount of this contribution is still under debate.

Problems arising from residual motion and motion correction

As shown in detail in a previous article²⁰ thorough motion correction is very important for correct interpretation of DGE effects. Without motion correction, we could observe an effect strength of 2 % in tumor, which dropped to 0.4 % after motion correction. Our motion correction was optimized (Figure 3), but a detailed analysis regarding potential residual motion artifacts in the Δ DGE maps was also performed for patient 1 and 3 (see Supporting Information). In this analysis, we applied several motion patterns to the data and compared the synthetic results, dubbed pseudo DGE, to the actual measured DGE ρ signal (Supporting Figures S1 - S13). Even though some similar pseudo DGE patterns could be generated, the contrast in the DGE ρ maps could not be completely explained by residual motion artifacts (Supporting Figures S4 and S11). Still in patient 3, the statistical evidence decreased when tested against synthetic pseudo effects due to uncorrected motion (Supporting Figure S11). The full analysis of these motion patterns and statistical tests can be found in the Supporting Information.

For the retrospective motion correction algorithm, we chose the voxel-based mutual information metric in combination with a rigid transform using six degrees of freedom. As glucose injection alters the intensity (by approx. 0.4% in tumors), in principle motion correction can be affected by this change. However, as we used a large number of spatial samples for the metric, and given the relatively small signal change only in a small part of the acquired volume, we think that this effect lies below the accuracy of retrospective motion correction. In addition, if a tissue type would change its contrast in a global

manner, it would not affect the metric, as only the number of appearances of a specific voxel value and not the value itself is important for the joint histogram, which is used to calculate the mutual information⁴⁰. A more severe effect could be non-rigidity, as the ventricles can undergo volumetric changes after the glucose injection¹⁴. Edge-based registration methods would be hampered in their performance, because rigid transformations cannot correct for these non-linear deformations. These volumetric changes can hinder the evaluation of the DGE contrast close to the ventricles; but on the other hand, non-linear transformations in the motion correction algorithm would be a potential source of a false contrast if e.g. small deformations in the tumor region would lead to spatial local maxima in the mutual information. Another drawback of retrospective motion correction is the required interpolation of voxels after the transformation. This interpolation can reduce small effects, which is why a higher order spline interpolation was used for the final interpolation of the registered images. Still, motion as well as motion correction can in principle alter the contrast as discussed in detail in the supporting information, where all motion correction parameters can also be found. Prospective motion correction steps could potentially help to further stabilize the experiment. Here, the patient interaction should be minimal (e.g. navigator scans), as the glucose injection experiment itself can already be irritating for the patients.

Methodological advances and experience with effect strength and stability at 3T

Readout

The major methodological change compared to previous studies at UHF^{14,16,17} besides the saturation scheme is the 3D snapshot CEST readout. Only with a 3D readout, can an accurate image based registration algorithm for retrospective motion correction be applied. Previous 2D approaches without prospective motion correction cannot assure a contrast that arises solely from CEST effects; therefore, these previous results have to be interpreted with care. Aiming for a snapshot, the acquired 3D volume in our study is rather small (60 mm) and still requires a slab selective pulse, which has a non-uniform excitation. This leads to problems for larger motions as even motion corrected slices can have different intensity (see slices 1-3 and 10-12 in Supporting Figure S16). This artifact, as well as coil sensitivity changes due to motion, could partly be mitigated by introducing

an interleaved M_0 scan for dynamic normalization similar to the method of Jones et al.⁴¹ for highly sampled Z-spectra. Using a gradient echo sequence as readout is beneficial in terms of robustness resulting in high temporal SNR, with the additional feature of simultaneously acquired phase information, which can be used for a dynamic B_0 correction. While this technique was proposed for Z-spectra acquisition previously³⁰, it was successfully translated to dynamic CEST imaging herein, by using dynamic images at multiple frequency offsets.

The proposed method thus forms a novel state of the art for dynamic CEST imaging. Still, several improvements would be desirable: a whole brain method without slab selection would overcome uncorrectable motion artifacts even for larger motions. A method that allows whole brain coverage but still provides snapshot ability is the recently developed EPI CEST of Akbey et al.⁴²

Due to the inherent lower SNR at clinical field strength, the voxel size of the snapshot-CEST sequence had to be increased in all three dimensions compared to 9.4 T to achieve a reasonable SNR. However, with bigger voxels, partial volume effects are more present, which poses a challenge for motion correction algorithms. Thus, a snapshot sequence with the same SNR but more volume coverage and higher resolution is the required next step.

CEST/CESL preparation

Due to the high exchange rate of the $-OH$ groups and the rather small chemical shift (1.2 ppm), the CEST effect is broad and suffers a lot from direct water saturation, especially at 3 T. Here, the SL pulses are beneficial, as they can be applied at a rather high B_1 , and still produce less direct water saturation since they restore the magnetization after the locking pulse. By doing so, signal changes close to the water resonance frequency can be detected. As shown by Jin et al.⁸ SL pulses are able to detect signal changes due to an increase of glucose concentration by only 1.5 mmol/L in vivo at UHF, while for a reliable detection with classical CEST an increase of ~ 17 mmol/L was required¹⁰. This sensitivity enhancement of CESL against classical CEST is even higher at lower field strengths. As classical SL can be sensitive to B_0 and B_1 inhomogeneities, the adiabatic SL pulse optimized herein forms a robust implementation of off-resonant SL on a clinical

system. Due to the adiabatic tilting, the pulses work both on- and off-resonant and can be chosen freely. Relatively low locking powers are also possible. The optimal parameters for saturation were defined using Bloch simulations²¹ to be close to 0.6 ppm with T_{rec} of 4 s; TSL = 120 ms and $B_1 = 4 \mu\text{T}$. This is similar to the TSL = 50 ms and $B_1 = 5 \mu\text{T}$ of Schuenke et al.¹⁷. The optimal offset around 0.6 ppm seems to be in the most coalescent region of the water protons and the –OH groups, thus our protocol is in some way similar to an on-resonant SL experiment. However, as we apply the pulses slightly off-resonant we achieve a lower direct water saturation and the effective $T_{1\rho}$ is longer. Therefore, we can apply longer saturation pulses without losing too much SNR. Another protocol with a similar saturation time is presented in Jin et al.³², who used SL with $B_1 \approx 11.5 \mu\text{T}$ and TSL= 50 ms in animal experiments.

In a previous glucoCEST study at 3 T, Wang et al.⁴³ showed glucose uptake using a similar saturation scheme with a short but relatively strong pulse ($t_{\text{sat}} = 48 \text{ ms}$, $B_1 = 2 \mu\text{T}$). However, the reported results use the MTR_{asym} metric, which cannot be directly compared to our study, which uses single offset measurements.

Although a longer TSL could yield more glucose weighting, we optimized our saturation time by the effective signal value as well. As longer saturation leads to lower z-magnetization, we used a compromise of glucose weighting and SNR. Another property of the used adiabatic pulses is that the adiabatic frequency sweep also labels exchanging protons at other resonance frequencies. For the injection experiments, this is not an issue since selection is achieved by contrast injection and not by the chemical shift.

Instead of SL, longer CEST saturation pulses with lower power are typically used and also yield similar DGE effect strength¹⁹ in 2D methods. Another approach for less direct water saturation in glucoCEST experiments was published recently by Xu et al. using an on-resonance variable delay multi-pulse scheme⁴⁴.

Conclusion

DGE ρ imaging was translated from UHF and optimized for a clinical field strength of 3 T, and a robust protocol was established for broader application. To achieve this, several obstacles were addressed, including sufficient signal to noise ratio, robustness of contrast, and post processing, especially motion correction. Early experience shows that DGE ρ seems possible at 3 T, and could not only be attributed to motion artifacts. The observed DGE ρ maps in two glioblastoma patients showed unique patterns, partly matching with the T1-ce tumor ring enhancement. However, effect sizes are small and careful application and evaluation is necessary. The developed sequence forms a first robust protocol for broader application in clinical studies.

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Tables

	A)	B)	C)
In-plane voxel size [mm ²]	1.7	2	2
Bandwidth [Hz/px]	400	400	700
TE/TR [ms]	2.5/5	2.5/5	2/4
Mean SNR in GM	86.66	118.48	107.52
Mean SNR in WM	92.59	123.09	114.30
Mean SNR in CSF	93.00	112.42	102.19

Table 1: SNR for different sequence parameters in different tissues. Tissue segmentation was performed in SPM using the saturated image at 0.6 ppm.

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Figures

Figure 1 Optimization of the HSExp pulse for 3 T. (a-c) Sum of squared deviations (SSD) to an analytical $T_{1\rho}$ - spectrum, which were used for pulse optimization²². Parameters resulting in a minimal SSD were $\Delta f = 2.5$ kHz, $\mu = 65$ and $t_{\text{window}} = 3.5$ ms, marked with a red square. (d) The SL cluster at 0 ppm for a TSL = 120 ms. (e) Measured Z-spectra and their standard error for this pulse cluster in a WM and GM ROI. DGE ρ Offsets acquired in the dynamic experiment are marked with a dashed line (0.6, 0.9, 1.2 and 1.5 ppm)

Figure 2 SNR maps of the snapshot CEST readout with different sequence parameters. A, B and C refer to the entries in Table 1

Figure 3 (a) Difference of source and reference image [a.u.] after motion correction for SPM, elastix and AFNI algorithms. Visually, elastix produces the best results with the fewest visible artifacts. The AFNI and SPM results contain more residual motion (e.g. red arrows). (b) Mean value and the standard deviation of all the voxels inside the brain in the corresponding the difference images. The standard deviation after the elastix algorithm is the lowest, confirming that this algorithm produces the fewest artifacts

Figure 4 Effect of motion correction, interleaved M_0 and dynamic B_0 correction. (a) ΔDGE_{ρ} [%] map of a volunteer measurement (image number 16 at $\Delta\omega = 0.9$ ppm) after motion correction. Here, the entire left hemisphere seems is affected by a strong hypointensity. (b) ΔDGE_{ρ} map with a normalization to the corresponding image at -300 ppm. Here the image is more flat, but still shows slight correlation with B_0 (d), especially in the anterior part. (c) ΔDGE_{ρ} map with the same normalization as (b) and an additional B_0 correction as proposed in Windschuh et al.³⁰. The dynamic B_0 correction normalizes the anterior part that is hypointense in (b). (d) ΔB_0 map [ppm] relative to the beginning of the measurement. (e) Histogram for the images in (a-c)

Figure 5 (a) Gd-enhanced T_1 image registered to the saturated CEST image (c). ROIs were drawn in a Gd-enhanced (gdce), necrosis and normal appearing WM region (naWM). (b) Mean and standard error of $\Delta DGE\rho$ signal in each ROI. The gdce and necrosis ROI show a positive $DGE\rho$ contrast after the injection. The asterisk indicates the time point of the $DGE\rho$ map in Figure 9d. (d) Patient motion. After a severe motion, the contrast is heavily affected, despite motion and field shift corrections. $\Delta DGE\rho$ images at different time points are shown in the top row

Figure 6 (a) Gd-enhanced T_1 weighted image registered to the saturated CEST image (c). As this patient showed no Gd-enhancement, only two ROIs were drawn in a normal appearing WM (naWM) and a hypointense region (hypo) in the T_1 -ce image. (b) $DGE\rho$ contrast curves show only minor change. The asterisk indicates the time point of the $DGE\rho$ map in Figure 9h. (d) Movement during the measurement. Please note, that the axis limits are different than in Figure 5. $\Delta DGE\rho$ images at different time points are shown in the top row

Figure 7 (a) shows again the Gd-enhanced T_1 image registered to the saturated CEST image (c). Two ROIs are drawn in a Gd-enhanced (gdce) and normal appearing WM region. The $DGE\rho$ contrast in the gdce ROI increases after the start of the injection, while the WM ROI does not show any changes (b). The asterisk indicates the time point of the $DGE\rho$ map in figure 9j. The movement during the measurement is shown in (d). $\Delta DGE\rho$ images at different time points are shown in the top row

Figure 8 (a) p-values for rejecting the null hypothesis that the mean values in the gdce ROI are equal to zero. (b) p-values for rejecting the null hypothesis that the mean values in the gdce ROI are equal with the mean values in the WM ROI

Figure 9 T₂-FLAIR (a,e,i), T₁-ce(b,f,j), T₁-ce with overlaid $\Delta DGE\rho$ map (c,g,k) and the $\Delta DGE\rho$ -maps (d,h,l) of patient 1 (a-d), 2 (e-h) and 3 (i-l)

Supporting Information

Dynamic glucose-enhanced (DGE) MRI at 3 T – method development and early clinical experience in the human brain

Parameters of motion correction algorithms

AFNI: The *3dvolreg* function was used with the following command line arguments:

-heptic

-twopass

-maxite 500

-clipit

-coarserot

SPM: Parameters for the *coreg* algorithm were chosen as follows:

Cost function: *Normalized mutual information*

Separation: *[7 4 2]*

Histogram Smoothing: *[7 7]*

elastix: The elastix parameter file contained the following entries for registration and reslicing:

(FixedInternallImagePixelType "float")

(MovingInternallImagePixelType "float")

(UseDirectionCosines "true")

(Registration "MultiResolutionRegistration")

(Interpolator "BSplineInterpolator")

(ResampleInterpolator "FinalBSplineInterpolator")

(Resampler "DefaultResampler")

(FixedImagePyramid "FixedRecursiveImagePyramid")

(MovingImagePyramid "MovingRecursiveImagePyramid")

(Optimizer "AdaptiveStochasticGradientDescent")
(Transform "EulerTransform")
(Metric "AdvancedMattesMutualInformation")
(AutomaticScalesEstimation "false")
(AutomaticTransformInitialization "false")
(HowToCombineTransforms "Compose")
(NumberOfHistogramBins 16)
(ErodeMask "false")
(NumberOfResolutions 4)
(ImagePyramidSchedule 16 16 8 4 4 4 2 2 2 1 1 1)
(MaximumNumberOfIterations 1000)
(NumberOfSpatialSamples 4000)
(NewSamplesEveryIteration "true")
(ImageSampler "Random")
(BSplineInterpolationOrder 3)
(FinalBSplineInterpolationOrder 3)
(DefaultPixelValue 0)
(WriteResultImage "true")
(ResultImagePixelFormat "float")
(ResultImageFormat "nii")

In depth analysis of influences of movement on the dynamic glucoCEST signal

Residual motion can have a strong influence on the contrast, especially at tissue interfaces, as previously shown by a baseline analysis¹. Therefore, a detailed analysis of possible residual motion artifacts in the acquired DGE data is necessary to be able to draw further conclusions regarding the DGE signal interpretation. To address these issues, an in-depth analysis of the observed movement for patient 1 and 3 is shown in the following. Patient 2 was not included as the observed motion was negligible.

Supporting Figure S1 shows the DGE signal without motion correction (a) and with motion correction (b) for patient 1 at slice number 8. Without motion correction, many artifacts arise and drawing conclusions is impossible. These artifacts are greatly reduced by motion correction (Figure S1b). However, the signal after motion correction could still be affected by residual uncorrected motion. The remaining question we want to answer here is: are the remaining signals due to glucose uptake or due to residual uncorrected motion?

Supporting Figure S1: DGE from uncorrected (a) vs motion corrected images (b) for patient 1 at slice 8. The co-registered T1-gdce (left) and FLAIR (right) image are shown in the last row.

Using the output of the motion correction algorithm, we can – by inversion of the detected transformations – generate the actual motion transformations that would move the initial volume to each of the moved volumes of the dynamic scan. This allows us to study the effects that the difference method DGE produces only due to motion, without any influence due to the administered glucose; we call this a pseudo CEST signal. More details of this synthetic approach can be found in the previous study¹.

Three different motion patterns were studied in this analysis, which were all applied to the first acquired image at the offset at 0.6 ppm. In the first pattern, the full motion transformation is applied to the baseline image. The second pattern applies the same motion transformation, but reduced by a factor of 10 in magnitude. To do so, the transformation parameters, namely translation in x, y and z direction and pitch roll and yaw angle, were extracted from the transformation matrix, divided by 10 and subsequently used to generate a new transformation matrix. This approach mimics a motion correction with residual errors in the actual moving direction. In the third pattern the same movement as in the second pattern was used, but the transform parameters were inverted before the division by 10. This mimics an overcorrection by the motion correction algorithm. These three patterns were compared to the actual calculated DGE signal using the same ROIs as in the main manuscript.

Supporting Figure S2 shows the actual DGE signal (a) and the pseudo DGE Signal for the full movement (b), one tenth of the full movement (c) and the inverse one tenth movement (d) for slice number 8. The hyper-intensity pattern observed in the motion corrected DGE image (Supporting Figure S2a) could not be reproduced with these motion patterns (for statistical analysis see Supporting Figure S4). Still, when looking at the full motion, some parts of the tumor ring enhancement appear bright and intensities are in the same order of magnitude as the DGE data. The principle pseudo CEST pattern stays the same when reducing the motion to one tenth, yet the pseudo effect size decreases by an order of magnitude (Supporting Figure S2c).

In both Supporting Figures S2a and S2b the ventricle appears hypointense, especially after image number 15. This could be a hint that there is still some residual motion that could not be corrected. However, a possible explanation could also be the volumetric change of the ventricle after the glucose injection. Since this slice is at the top edge of the ventricle and the slice is rather thick (5 mm), this change could have an influence on the contrast. These non-linear ventricular deformations cannot be corrected retrospectively by the used rigid registration motion correction algorithm.

Supporting Figure S2: DGE (a) and pseudo DGE signal for the full movement (b), one tenth (c) and inverse one tenth movement (d) of patient 1 at slice 8. . The co-registered T1-gdce (left) and FLAIR (right) image are shown in the last row of each subplot.

Supporting Figure S3 shows the same patterns but for the entire volume (slices 1-12) at offset number 20. The pseudo CEST signal with the full motion shows hyperintensities in the ventral and medial region of the tumor rim. In contrast to the actually measured DGE signal (especially slices 7 and 8), the dorsal part of the tumor rim appears hypointense in Figure S3b. The hypointensity in the necrosis region in slices 4-6 in Figure S3a does not appear in any of the pseudo CEST maps.

Supporting Figure S3: DGE (a) and pseudo DGE signal for the full movement (b), one tenth (c) and inverse one tenth movement (d) of patient 1 at image number 20. (e) and (f) show the co-registered T1-gdce and FLAIR image, respectively.

In addition to the visual analysis, the correlation of the voxels in a tumor ROI was tested. Pearson's linear correlation coefficient was computed for the real DGE signal against all three pseudo CEST patterns. The same offset as in Supporting Figure S3 was used. The ROI was drawn in slice number 8 in the T_1 -gdce image, containing all tumor voxels. The correlation plots are shown in Supporting Figure S4, for the correlation with the full motion (Figure S4a), one tenth of the motion (Figure S4b) and the inverse one tenth of the motion (Figure S4c). The voxel intensities of the real measured DGE signal are projected onto the x-axis, the different pseudo CEST voxel values on the y-axis. The correlation coefficients are not significantly different from 0 which shows that the measured DGE signal is not correlated with the pseudo CEST signals.

Supporting Figure S4: Correlation of the real DGE signal voxels in a tumor ROI with the full motion (a), one tenth of the motion (b) and the inverse one tenth of the motion (c). R and p stand for the Pearson correlation coefficient and the corresponding p-value, respectively

To provide a dynamic insight in the pseudo effects patterns due to motion, the ROIs from Figure 5 in the main text were used to investigate the signal change in these ROIs. The actual DGE signal and the pseudo signals are shown in Supporting Figures S5-S7 where the gdce ROI is investigated in Supporting Figure S5, the necrosis ROI in Supporting Figure S6 and the normal appearing WM ROI in Supporting Figure S7. As expected from Supporting Figure S2, the signal change due to motion is hardly correlated with the real DGE signal. In addition, the magnitude is much lower, even after the severe motion at offset number 25. Of course, the DGE signal could still be affected by other factors that change between different images like noise or different partial volume effects. However, it is interesting that, in the given ROI, the signal change in the pseudo CEST is rather low compared to the real DGE signal. The pseudo CEST signals using

one tenth of the movement – which is an amount we think is realistic after the motion correction – are another order of magnitude lower.

Supporting Figure S5: DGE and pseudo DGE signal in a gdce ROI

In contrast to the gdce ROI, the necrosis ROI of Supporting Figure S6 shows a pseudo CEST signal in the same order of magnitude as the actual measured DGE signal, but only for the full movement. Again, after measurement 25, the signal is heavily affected. The pseudo signals in the patterns with one tenth of the movement are extremely low.

Supporting Figure S6: DGE and pseudo DGE signal in a necrosis ROI

The same analysis for the WM ROI is shown in Supporting Figure S7. While the patterns with one tenth of the movement again show low signal changes, the full movement creates a pseudo signal which has some similarities to the pseudo CEST signal in Supporting Figure S6. However, the magnitude and the standard error are much lower, which is probably due to the more homogeneous tissue surrounding the ROI. Nevertheless, it is important to note that residual motion can introduce similar signal changes in different regions of the brain (e.g. see measurements no. 20-27 in Supporting Figures S6 and S7).

Supporting Figure S7: DGE and pseudo DGE in a normal appearing WM ROI

Having analyzed patient 1 in detail, the same analysis was applied for patient 3. Patient 2 was not further investigated here, as almost no DGE signal and motion was detected. For patient 3, Supporting Figure S8 shows the completely uncorrected DGE signal (Supporting Figure S8a) versus the corrected (Supporting Figure S8b) at slice number 8. As in Supporting Figure S1, interpretation of the uncorrected DGE image is hampered. A more detailed investigation of the motion follows in Supporting Figures S9-S13.

Supporting Figure S8: DGE from uncorrected (a) vs motion corrected images (b) for patient 3 at slice 8. The co-registered T1-gdce (left) and FLAIR (right) image are shown in the last row.

The pseudo CEST using the full motion generates hypointensities at the tumor rim (Figure S8b); this is similar to the findings in patient 1. Again, the ventral part appears hyperintense, which could also be seen in the real DGE signal (Figure S8a). However, the dorsal part of the tumor rim appears hypointense in the pseudo CEST map, while in the DGE maps, the entire tumor rim shows a hyperintensity, especially after image number 20.

Another similarity to patient 1 in the real DGE signal is the hypointense CSF region. This could partly be reproduced in the pseudo CEST contrast for both ventricles, especially in the ventral part. As this patient has a large edema region around the tumor, the images are prone to motion artifacts due to the large intensity gradients resulting from the large T_2 of the edema compared to tissue. This is particularly apparent in the full motion pseudo CEST. However, the real DGE signal also shows hyperintensities surrounding the tumor, which could indicate residual motion artifacts. Again, the one tenth pseudo CEST motion contrast is an order of magnitude lower.

Supporting Figure S9: DGE (a) and pseudo DGE signal for the full movement (b), one tenth (c) and inverse one tenth (d) movement of patient 3 at slice 8. . The co-registered T1-gdce (left) and FLAIR (right) image are shown in the last row of each subplot.

The full 3D volume of patient 3 is shown in Supporting Figure S10. As seen in Supporting Figure S9, there is a mismatch between the intensities in the dorsal tumor rim in the real and pseudo DGE signal for the full movement in slice 8. This is also true but harder to detect visibly for slice 7 and 9. In slice number 11, the signal pattern is more similar as the entire tumor lights up in Supporting Figures S10a and S10b and a more ventral region of the brain appears also hyperintense in both contrasts. However, these outer slices are hard to interpret because of the slab selection. In addition, the hypointensity in the left side of the brain in the pseudo signal is not visible in the real DGE signal.

Supporting Figure S10: DGE (a) and pseudo DGE signal for the full movement (b), one tenth (c) and inverse one tenth movement (d) of patient 3 at image number 25. (e) and (f) show the co-registered T1-gdce and FLAIR image, respectively.

Supporting Figure S11 shows the same correlation analysis as Supporting Figure S4 for patient 3. Here the offset at image number 25 was used for the analysis, which is shown in Supporting Figure S10. The correlation is actually significantly different from 0 with p-values < 0.005 for all motion patterns. However, the correlation is very weak with a maximum coefficient of determination $R^2 = 2.52\%$ for the inverse one tenth motion pattern. Nevertheless, according to this correlation, we must take into account that residual motion artifacts might still partially contribute to the real measured DGE contrast. The match with the positive transformation lets us conclude that it is more probable that residual motion was not corrected for instead of overcorrected in this case.

Supporting Figure S11: Correlation of the real DGE signal voxels in a tumor ROI with the full motion (a), one tenth of the motion (b) and the inverse one tenth of the motion (c). R and p stand for the Pearson correlation coefficient and the corresponding p-value, respectively.

The DGE signal in the gdce ROI is shown in Supporting Figure S12. Even though the full motion shows very bright spots in the contrast maps, the pseudo DGE signal change is very low. Here, the hyperintense ventral part and the hypointense dorsal part of the tumor rim seem to balance out, which would also explain the high standard error. As expected, the one tenth movements have again negligible influence.

Supporting Figure S12: DGE and pseudo DGE signal in a gdce ROI

The DGE signal change in the WM ROI is very low for both, the real and the pseudo CEST time series. Here, we would not expect any residual motion artifacts in the real DGE signal.

Supporting Figure S13: DGE and pseudo DGE signal in a WM ROI

In conclusion, we examined if it is possible to generate the observed DGE effects purely by reasonable residual motion. Even though we were able to generate pseudo CEST effects in similar order of magnitude at some tissue interfaces, the entire slice or volume never showed the same pseudo contrast pattern as observed in the measured DGE maps. If the same hypo- and hyperintense patterns as in the motion corrected DGE maps had appeared in the generated pseudo DGE maps, this would have been a clear indicator that the observed DGE effects are actual pseudo effects due to motion. Thus, we were not able to falsify the observed DGE contrast. It could be that other residual motion patterns are introduced by the

motion correction algorithm, other than one tenth of the detected motion or the inverse of that. Nevertheless, the tested one tenth and inverse one tenth motion patterns only lead to weak pseudo effects, which is why we would also not expect much bigger effects if this amount of motion would be in a different direction. We could not find a significant correlation between the real DGE signal and the pseudo CEST signal in a tumor ROI for patient 1. For patient 3 a very weak correlation was found in the tumor ROI. In contrast, the ROI analysis over time for real and pseudo CEST DGE showed completely different values. Still, all used statistics remain hypothetical as we have no real measured data of the motion, and could only estimate the possible residual movement for both patients.

According to these observations, we determined that we could not falsify a detectable glucose uptake at 3T.

Correlation of DGE contrast with Gadolinium enhancement

As previous work assumed, DGE signal contrast is mainly due to glucose molecules that leak through the blood-brain-barrier into the extracellular space, similar to Gd contrast agents^{2,3}. Therefore, one would assume a correlation between the Δ DGE map and the contrast enhanced T_{1w} image. To investigate this potential correlation, we performed a voxel-wise analysis in two different ROIs in the Δ DGE map and the T_{1-CE} enhanced image. Given the hypothesis that a region that accumulates more Gd should also accumulate more glucose in the extracellular space and therefore appears brighter in both images, so the voxel intensities of both images should be correlated. However, we did not find a correlation that is significant different from 0, using a rejection threshold of $p < 0.005$ for patient 1 (Supporting Figure S14), neither for the Gd ROI (Figure S14a), nor for an ROI containing the entire tumor (S14b). The Δ DGE map used for correlation was the same as in Supporting Figure S3. Supporting Figures S14c and S14d show the corresponding ROI for the analysis in Figure S14a and Figure S14b, respectively.

Supporting Figure S14: Voxel-wise correlation of the ΔDGE map and the T_1 -ce image of patient 1 in a gdce ROI (a) and a whole-tumor ROI (b). Panels (c) and (d) show the corresponding ROI for the analysis in (a) and (b), respectively.

The same correlation was analyzed for patient 3. As seen in Supporting Figure S15, we were again not able to observe a significant correlation. Neither the Gd ROI (Figure S15a) nor the whole tumor ROI (Figure S15b) showed a correlation that is significant different from 0. Supporting Figures S15c and S15d show the corresponding ROI for the analysis in Figures S15a and S15b, respectively. The ΔDGE map used for correlation was the same as in Supporting Figure S10.

In conclusion, we were not able to find a significant correlation between the intensity of ΔDGE and Gd enhanced voxels.

Supporting Figure S15: Voxel-wise correlation of the ΔDGE map and the $T1$ -ce image of patient 3 in a $gdce$ ROI (a) and a whole tumor ROI (b). Panels (c) and (d) show the corresponding ROI for the analysis in (a) and (b), respectively

3D Analysis of Δ DGE maps

The whole 3D volume of the Δ DGE map from Figure 9 d,h,l with the co-registered T₁-ce images in Figures 5a, 6a and 7a from the main manuscript is shown in Supporting Information Figure S16. For patient 1 (top row) an overlap with Gd enhancement can be seen in slices 6-9. However, due to the motion of the patient, residual artifacts appear at the outermost slices, due to the slab selection of the snapshot-CEST sequence: if motion occurs the slab excited before injection and the slab excited after injection is different and as the profile is no longer rectangular at the edges, deviations are observed. Patient 2 results (middle row) showed less artifact, but they are still visible in the lowest and highest slices. Results for patient 3 show various hyper-intense regions, corresponding to Gd enhancement in slices 7 and 8. However, this was not observed in lower slices. The visual overlap with Gd is in general lower compared to that observed in patient 1.

Supporting Figure S166. First column: Co-registered T_1 -ce images of patient 1 (top), patient 2 (middle) and patient 3 (bottom). Second column: ΔDGE maps [%] of patient 1 (top), patient 2 (middle) and patient 3 (bottom). While the center slices (5-8) show a stable contrast, the outer slices are partly affected due to different slab selection after motion. This cannot be retrospectively corrected at the moment.

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